

Traffic Analysis of Local 5G Networks Using PCAP-Based Measurement

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Abstract: This study introduces a packet-level analysis of video distribution traffic generated by two user terminals operating within a Local 5G network configured for Time Division Duplex (TDD) synchronization. In TDD-based systems, radio-channel allocation is typically configured with a greater proportion of downlink slots and fewer uplink slots. The experiment assumes a combined video transmission rate of 14–20 Mbps for the two terminals, under conditions characterized by low delay jitter and no packet loss.

Fig. 1: TDD Synchronization

Keywords: Local 5G, TDD Synchronization

Bulk processing of frames through the Local 5G network can lead to video decoding noise, as illustrated in the following figure.

Fig. 2: Bulk Processing frames

The aggregated traffic from a single UE transmitted through the Local 5G network is illustrated in the following figure.

1. UE x1

Focusing on the graph with a sampling rate of 30 ms, there are alternating periods of incoming traffic (> 0 bytes) and no incoming

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Fig. 3: Resolution 1000ms , 100ms

Fig. 4: Resolution 30ms, 10ms traffic (= 0 bytes) in nearly the same proportions and sequence. A similar pattern is observed with a sampling rate of 10 ms.

Therefore, even with two UEs, the additional traffic could occupy the zero-byte intervals, suggesting the potential for stable communication without contention.

2. UE x2

However, something appeared to be abnormal in the system or

Fig. 5: Resolution 1000ms UE0, UE1

Fig. 6: Resolution 1000ms UE0, UE1 Zoom-In

Fig. 7: Resolution 100ms UE0, UE1

Fig. 8: Resolution 10ms UE0, UE1

network behavior. When focusing on the graph with a sampling rate of 1,000 ms (zoomed-in view) Fig.6, the traffic from the two UEs, which had been well-shaped during stable periods, temporarily lost synchronization and failed to maintain the same level of shaping. After this brief disturbance, the shaping recovered and the traffic returned to a stable state. Notably, video decoding noise was observed exactly at the moment of this instability.

When there is a single UE, scheduling occurs in 5-ms cycles Fig.9, and only a small portion of bandwidth is utilized immediately after each scheduling event. This behavior is likely caused by the scheduling or algorithmic overhead inherent in the system.

Fig. 9: UE x1 Scheduling Cycles

When there are two UEs Fig.10 and the traffic is stable,

Fig. 10: UE x2 Scheduling Cycles

As shown in the Fig.11 (TDD synchronization ratio: uplink 4 / downlink 14), uplink slots 4 and 14 are allocated to UE0, and uplink slots 5 and 15 are allocated to UE1 under stable traffic conditions.

Fig. 11: TDD Details

When there are two UEs and the traffic transitions from stable to unstable,

Fig. 12: UE x2, scheduling cycles — unstable

Therefore, one possible cause of instability is the collapse of the scheduling cycle, which may occur due to fluctuations in radio reception levels or other environmental factors.

We have described the mechanism by which video noise is generated as a result of bulk frame processing caused by TDD synchronization, scheduling overhead, and cycle irregularities, even when sufficient bandwidth is available in the network or system.

Although the TDD synchronization process is generally implemented and designed to be optimal for typical applications, in systems dominated by uplink traffic—such as the scenario discussed in this paper—we found that the overhead associated with uplink channel scheduling has a significant impact on overall system quality.

This situation could be improved by applying extended scheduling techniques, such as Semi-Persistent Scheduling (SPS) and Configured Grant (CG) as defined in 3GPP Release 16, which allow UEs to transmit uplink data without sending scheduling requests or waiting for uplink grants.

The gNB can configure Configured Grant (CG) parameters for each UE, allowing the UEs to transmit uplink data within the assigned CG resources without sending scheduling requests (SR) or waiting for an uplink grant, as specified in 3GPP Release 16.

As a personal note, I found the process of analyzing these behaviors both technically challenging and highly enjoyable.

Listing 1: setup.py

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3
# encoding: utf-8

from distutils.core import setup, Extension

setup(name='pypcap',
      version='0.1.0',
      description='pypcap analyze module',
      author='mixi',
      author_email='dsugisawa',
      url='https://github.com/xflagstudio/',
      ext_modules=
        [Extension(
            'pypcap',
            ['pypcap.cc'],
            include_dirs=['/usr/local/include/'],
            libraries=['pcap'],
            extra_compile_args=[''])])
```

Listing 2: graph.py

```
import sys
import os
import pypcap
from matplotlib import pyplot
import numpy as np

pcap_meta = []

def callback(s):
    pcap_meta.append(s)

pypcap.pcap_analyze(sys.argv[1], int(sys.argv[3]),
                    callback)

resolution = float(sys.argv[2])
start = int(sys.argv[4])
stop = int(sys.argv[5])

mm = {}

for r in pcap_meta:
    key = int(r[0]/resolution)
    val = int(r[1] / 1024)

    if key >= start and key <= stop:
        if key in mm:
            # print("exists ", key, mm[key], val)
            mm[key] += val
        else:
            # print("insert ", key, mm[key])
            mm[key] = val

y0 = mm.values()
x0 = mm.keys()
```

```
pyplot.title(os.path.basename(sys.argv[1]))
pyplot.xlabel('time(relative) resolution ' + str(
    resolution) + ' usec')
pyplot.ylabel('rate(KB)')
pyplot.plot(x0, y0)
pyplot.ylim(0, 200)
pyplot.xticks(np.arange(min(list(x0)), max(list(x0)),
    50))

pyplot.show()
```

3. pcap-analyze-tools

3.1 Overview

The pypcap/Python extension enables highly efficient, frame-by-frame packet analysis for Local 5G traffic.

Listing 3: Build

```
python3 setup.py build_ext --inplace
```

Listing 4: Usage

```
python ./graph.py ~/Downloads/sample.pcapng 10000 50003
8000 8300
```

3.2 Arguments

- **pcap file path:** Path to the input .pcap/.pcapng file.
- **resolution (microseconds):** forSampling resolution in μ s (e.g., 10000 = 10 ms).
- **target port:** UDP/TCP destination port to analyze (e.g., video stream port).
- **sequence number start:** Lower bound of sequence number range to include.
- **sequence number stop:** Upper bound of sequence number range to include.

3.2.1 Dependencies

- **python3**
- **libpcap**

Listing 5: pypcap.cc

```

#include <unistd.h>
#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <string.h>
#include <ctype.h>
#include <time.h>
#include <memory.h>
#include <arpa/inet.h>
#include <sys/types.h>
#include <sys/errno.h>
#include <sys/socket.h>
#include <sys/time.h>
#include <netinet/tcp.h>
#include <netinet/udp.h>
#include <netinet/in.h>
#include <netinet/ip.h>
#include <net/ethernet.h>

#include <Python.h>

// pcap
#include <pcap.h>

static uint64_t first_epoch = 0;
static int udpport = 0;
static unsigned packet_size = 0;

/*
 0           1           2           3
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 1
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| magic(0xdeadbeaf) |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| data length      | data types |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| payload ....
+-----+-----
*/
// pcap - callback
static void pcap_callback(
    u_char* user,
    const struct pcap_pkthdr *h,
    const u_char *bytes
)
{
    char addrstr[64] = {0};
    struct ether_header *ethhdr = (struct ether_header *)bytes;
    struct ip *ipv4h = NULL;
    PyObject* callback = (PyObject*)user;

    if (!callback) {
        return;
    }
    if (h->caplen < (sizeof(*ipv4h) + sizeof(*ethhdr))) {
        return;
    }
    if (h->caplen != h->len) {
        return;
    }
    uint64_t t = h->ts.tv_sec * 1000000 + h->ts.tv_usec;
    if (first_epoch == 0) {
        first_epoch = t;
    }

    switch(ntohs(ethhdr->ether_type)) {
    case ETHERTYPE_IP:
        ipv4h = (struct ip *) (bytes + sizeof(struct ether_header));
        inet_ntop(AF_INET, &ipv4h->ip_src, addrstr, sizeof(addrstr) - 1);
        break;
    case ETHERTYPE_IPV6:
    default:
        return;
    }
    struct udphdr* udph = (struct udphdr*) (bytes + sizeof(struct ether_header) + 20);
    if (ntohs(udph->uh_dport) != udpport) {

```

```

    return;
}
int payload_len = (int)(ntohs(udph->uh_ulen) - sizeof(struct udphdr));
char* payload = (char*)(bytes + sizeof(struct ether_header) + 20 + sizeof(struct udphdr));

unsigned* header = (unsigned*)payload;
unsigned identifier = ntohl(header[0]);
int cameraIdentifier = ntohl(header[1]);
unsigned flags = (ntohl(header[2]) & (0x80000000));
unsigned seqnm = (ntohl(header[2]) & (0x7FFFFFFF));
unsigned length = ntohl(header[3]);

if (length <= 0 || length > 8192 || identifier != 0xdeadbeaf) {
    printf("invalid header try next. (%d,%d,%d,%d)",
        length, (int)seqnm, (int)cameraIdentifier, payload_len);
    return;
}

packet_size += length;
if (!(flags & (1<<31))) {
    return;
}

// callback tuple.
PyObject* tuple = PyTuple_New(2);
if (!tuple) {
    printf("tuple null..");
    return;
}
if (PyTuple_SetItem(tuple, 0, PyLong_FromLong(t - first_epoch)) != 0) {
    printf("failed set item .. 0");
    return;
}
if (PyTuple_SetItem(tuple, 1, PyLong_FromLong(packet_size)) != 0) {
    printf("failed set item .. 1");
    return;
}
PyObject_CallFunction(callback, "(O)", tuple);
Py_DECREF(tuple);
// init size <= 0
packet_size = 0;
return;
}

```